

Appendix A: Network architectures

We adopted a modified version of the inception network developed by Treyer et al. (2024) for the encoder network and the estimator network in our SCL framework. The detailed description of the inception network is presented therein. We designed a decoder that leverages bilinear interpolation for upsampling images. The architectures of the encoder, the estimator, and the decoder are presented in Fig. A.1.

Appendix B: Examples of probability density estimates

We present the probability density estimates obtained by CLAP for a few exemplar galaxies at different redshifts in Fig. B.1. We illustrate the outcomes with and without applying the re-fitting procedure, and before and after combining the ensemble using the harmonic mean. As shown, refitting preserves the global shape of each probability density estimate. There are many spikes in the raw estimates when the data are insufficient to populate the redshift bins, especially for the CFHTLS and KiDS datasets at high redshift. These unrealistic features can be effectively removed by the smoothing applied in refitting. There are non-negligible variations among the uncombined estimates due to unaccounted-for epistemic uncertainties. The combination using the harmonic mean takes into account the variations but does not aggregate the uncertainties. As demonstrated in the main text, both refitting and combining estimates using the harmonic mean do not introduce apparent biases or miscalibration.

Appendix C: Assessment on recalibration

The recalibration procedure is a crucial part in CLAP as it ensures good calibration for each data instance. We demonstrate its importance in Fig. C.1, where we compare the results with and without recalibration for the SDSS, CFHTLS, and KiDS datasets. These results are obtained by combining the ensemble of ten probability density estimates using the harmonic mean. As shown, although there seems to be no conspicuous difference with and without recalibration in terms of the point estimates z_{photo} , the recalibration procedure indeed improves the calibration of the obtained probability density estimates. Particularly for the KiDS dataset, the probability density estimates without recalibration would appear to be overdispersed, as indicated by the non-negligible cumulative offsets $\Delta F_{p_{\Sigma-h}}$ and the concave PIT distribution, while the estimates become much better calibrated after recalibration. Furthermore, we note that for over 90% of the probability density estimates, the required correction by recalibration is mild, equivalent to an amount of no more than a redshift bin Δz . This implies that the adaptive KNN algorithm may occasionally produce a biased k value that does not define a neighbourhood properly, yet the local recalibration is a remedy for this bias.

Appendix D: Statistics for point estimates

We present the global mean residual $\langle \delta z \rangle = \langle (z_{photo} - z_{spec}) / (1 + z_{spec}) \rangle$, σ_{MAD} , and the outlier fraction $\eta_{>\alpha}$ with $|\delta z| > \alpha$ for the photometric redshift point estimates obtained by all the methods presented in Fig. 6. The results for the SDSS, CFHTLS, and KiDS datasets are quoted in Tables D.1, D.2, and D.3, respectively. $\alpha = 0.05$ is adopted for the SDSS dataset, while $\alpha = 0.15$ is for the CFHTLS dataset and the KiDS dataset.

	$\langle \delta z \rangle$	σ_{MAD}	$\eta_{>0.05}$
CLAP	0.00005	0.00853	0.20%
SCL Prediction	0.00024	0.00850	0.21%
Inception Net + Bias Corr. (Lin et al. 2022)	0.00002	0.00919	0.41%
Inception Net (Pasquet et al. 2019)	0.00009	0.00915	0.31%
Capsule Net (Dey et al. 2022a)	0.00007	0.00898	0.19%
KNN + Regression (Beck et al. 2016)	0.00064	0.01342	1.36%

Table D.1. Statistics for the point estimates obtained by the methods presented in Sect. 4 for the SDSS dataset.

$z_{photo} < 1.0$	$\langle \delta z \rangle$	σ_{MAD}	$\eta_{>0.15}$
CLAP	0.00079	0.01499	0.75%
SCL Prediction	-0.00152	0.01488	0.74%
Inception Net + Bias Corr. (Lin et al. 2022)	-0.00375	0.01991	2.82%
Inception Net (Treyer et al. in prep.)	-0.00323	0.01455	0.78%
Le Phare	-0.00268	0.03271	1.67%
$z_{photo} > 1.0$	$\langle \delta z \rangle$	σ_{MAD}	$\eta_{>0.15}$
CLAP	0.01509	0.03156	7.42%
SCL Prediction	0.01221	0.03024	7.29%
Inception Net + Bias Corr. (Lin et al. 2022)	0.04133	0.06178	13.96%
Inception Net (Treyer et al. in prep.)	0.02861	0.02958	6.80%
Le Phare	0.06206	0.06394	14.60%

Table D.2. Statistics for the point estimates obtained by the methods presented in Sect. 4 for the CFHTLS dataset. The results with $z_{photo} < 1.0$ (covering roughly 90% of the full sample) and $z_{photo} > 1.0$ are shown separately.

$z_{photo} < 0.6$	$\langle \delta z \rangle$	σ_{MAD}	$\eta_{>0.15}$
CLAP	0.00011	0.01557	0.30%
CLAP (No NIR)	0.00006	0.01822	0.25%
SCL Prediction	-0.00087	0.01552	0.32%
Hybrid Net (Li et al. 2022a)	-0.00375	0.01447	0.25%
VGG Net (Li et al. 2022a)	0.00368	0.02428	0.35%
MLPQNA	0.00142	0.02518	1.06%
ANNz2	-0.01399	0.03436	3.13%
BPZ	-0.00327	0.03105	3.43%
$z_{photo} > 0.6$	$\langle \delta z \rangle$	σ_{MAD}	$\eta_{>0.15}$
CLAP	0.01712	0.04719	17.95%
CLAP (No NIR)	0.02491	0.07125	27.32%
SCL Prediction	0.01257	0.03375	12.80%
Hybrid Net (Li et al. 2022a)	0.02149	0.02745	9.94%
VGG Net (Li et al. 2022a)	0.02741	0.06612	25.61%
MLPQNA	0.01612	0.07637	30.34%
ANNz2	-0.05409	0.04152	17.97%
BPZ	0.02654	0.04484	14.33%

Table D.3. Statistics for the point estimates obtained by the methods presented in Sect. 4 for the KiDS dataset. The results with $z_{photo} < 0.6$ (covering roughly 90% of the full sample) and $z_{photo} > 0.6$ are shown separately.

Appendix E: Local spatial distribution of the nearest neighbours

For a finite latent space established by CLAP using a given training sample, how the nearest neighbours are spatially distributed in the local neighbourhood would differ for each query data instance because of uneven data coverage. In particular, the local spatial distributions of the nearest neighbours are likely to be skewed for query data instances close to or beyond the boundary of the established latent space, or located in regions with sparse data coverage, which may lead to biased estimation of probability densities.

Fig. A.1. Network architectures of the encoder, the estimator, and the decoder used in our work. The kernel size, the padding type, the activation function, and the output shape for each layer are specified when necessary. k and s refer to the kernel size and the output shape, respectively. In the encoder, c stands for the total number of channels after concatenating multi-band images and additional input ($c = 6$ for the SDSS dataset and the CFHTLS dataset; $c = 10$ for the KiDS dataset). The encoder outputs the latent vector v_A and the vector v_B with parallel fully connected layers. In the decoder, b stands for the number of optical bands for images ($b = 5$ for the SDSS dataset and the CFHTLS dataset; $b = 4$ for the KiDS dataset). The Leaky ReLU activation has a leaky ratio of 0.2. In the estimator, m stands for the number of redshift bins in the output (quoted in Table I).

To check this effect, we first leveraged an ‘odds’ ratio to characterise the local spatial distributions of the nearest neighbours, defined as follows. For each data instance, we determine the centre of mass C of its nearest neighbours in the latent space. We define a hyperplane that goes through the projection O of the given data instance and is also perpendicular to OC , the link between the two points. This hyperplane divides the local neighbourhood into two halves. Then, the odds ratio is defined as $r_{odds} = N_{\setminus C}/N_C$, where N_C is the number of the nearest neighbours falling in the half with C , and $N_{\setminus C}$ is the number of the nearest neighbours in the other half. A lower r_{odds} indicates a more skewed spatial distribution, while the r_{odds} of an even distribution is close to one.

For each of the SDSS, CFHTLS, and KiDS target samples, we compare two subsamples enclosed by two percentiles (i.e. 20th and 80th, respectively) from the overall r_{odds} distribution, using one of the ten CLAP models in the ensemble. These percentiles are selected so that the two subsamples represent the two ends of the r_{odds} distribution and the number of data instances in each subsample is not too low. The results are illustrated in Figs. E.1 and E.2. We found that the r_{odds} distributions for all the datasets are far from uniformity, with most data populated in the low r_{odds} bins. The shown results such as the cumulative offsets $\Delta F_{p\Sigma-h}$ and the PIT distributions give an impression that the probability densities from the two subsamples would not be as well calibrated as stated in the main text. However, these results

Fig. B.1. Examples of probability density estimates obtained by CLAP from the SDSS, CFHTLS, and KiDS datasets. *First column:* Examples of uncombined probability density estimates for galaxies at different redshifts from the SDSS dataset, randomly selected from one of the ten CLAP models in the ensemble. Comparison is made for the same galaxies with and without refitting. In each panel, the vertical dashed line indicates the spectroscopic redshift. *Second column:* Probability density estimates after refitting for the same galaxies in the first row. The ten uncombined estimates are shown in different colours, while the ones obtained by combining the ten estimates using the harmonic mean are shown in red. *Third and fourth columns:* Same as the first two rows, but from the CFHTLS dataset. *Fifth and sixth columns:* Same as the first two rows, but from the KiDS dataset.

may be simply under the impact of mismatch, since the r_{odds} -selected subsamples no longer follow the original redshift-data distribution for the training sample and the target sample. There may also be random errors due to low statistics. Therefore, these results do not conclusively indicate that the estimation of proba-

bility densities for either subsample is biased. In order to avoid artificially introducing extra biases, we did not make any selection on r_{odds} in our main experiments. To ensure the robustness of CLAP, future work will need to further investigate the local spatial distributions of the nearest neighbours in the latent space,

Fig. C.1. Same as Fig. 7 but showing the outcomes with and without recalibration implemented in CLAP. For each dataset, the ensemble of ten probability density estimates are combined using the harmonic mean.

and focus on evaluating the properties of the sparse regions and the boundary.

Fig. E.1. Comparisons between two subsamples selected by the odds ratio r_{odds} that characterises the local spatial distribution of the nearest neighbours of each data instance in the latent space (i.e. $r_{odds} < 20th\ percentile$ and $r_{odds} > 80th\ percentile$). The results are shown using the SDSS, CFHTLS, and KiDS target samples. For each dataset, only one of the ten CLAP models in the ensemble is selected for demonstration. *First row:* r_{odds} distributions. In each panel, the vertical dashed lines indicate the 20th and 80th percentiles of the distribution. *Second row:* Mean redshift residuals as a function of photometric redshift z_{photo} . Same as in Fig. 6 the results for the CFHTLS dataset and the KiDS dataset are shown in the low redshift ranges in addition to the full ranges. *Third row:* σ_{MAD} as a function of r -band magnitude. *Fourth row:* Cumulative offsets $\Delta F_{p\Sigma-h}$ between each of the stacked recentred probability densities $p_{\Sigma}(z - z_{photo})$ and the corresponding $z_{spec} - z_{photo}$ histogram.

Fig. E.2. Same as Fig. 5 but showing the comparisons between the two subsamples with $r_{\text{odds}} < 20\text{th percentile}$ and $r_{\text{odds}} > 80\text{th percentile}$. For each dataset, only one of the ten CLAP models in the ensemble is selected for demonstration.